

Instruction

You can earn a reward by responding to the following questionnaire.

For each question in the list, please select your preferred option from two alternatives (for example, "50% chance of 1000 Yen " vs. "400 Yen for sure ").

Before answering the questions, please refer to the following rules and guidelines for making selections.

The following example will help you understand how each question is handled.

Please consider the following scenario: You are faced with a list of questions, each presenting two options. Option A gives you a 50% chance of receiving 1,000 yen and a 50% chance of receiving 0 yen. Option B offers a guaranteed fixed reward. :

Q#		Option A	Option B
1	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	10 Yen for sure
2	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	20 Yen for sure
3	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	30 Yen for sure
...
98	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	980 Yen for sure
99	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	990 Yen for sure
100	Would you rather have:	50% chance of 1000 Yen	1000 Yen for sure

For each question, you choose between Option A (50% chance of receiving 1,000 yen and a 50% chance of receiving 0 yen) and Option B (guarantees a reward):

- After answering all 100 questions, the computer will randomly select one question from these 100, and your reward will be determined based on the choice you made for that question.
- Each question has an equal probability of being selected. There is no advantage to being dishonest in your responses; any dishonesty would result in a less favorable outcome if the question associated with that response is chosen.

You might initially select Option A for the first few questions and switch to Option B for the last few, indicating a change in preference at some point. To save time, please specify the question number at which you switch from Option A to Option B.

- Based on the question number at which you switch from Option A to Option B, the responses for all 100 questions will be completed accordingly. Your choice for all questions prior to that specified question will be Option A, and for that question and all subsequent questions, your choice will be treated as Option B.

The rewards accrued from this experiment will be disclosed after the conclusion of the next experiment and will be paid out along with the amount you earn in the subsequent experiment.